

The stereoselective *C*-alkylation of chiral nitronic acid (4*S**,5*R*)-(+)-4-(6-nitro-6-carbethoxymethyl)-5-[(1*R*)-menthyloxy]-3,4-dihydro-2(5*H*)-furanone

Lei Lei Zhang and Zhi Qiang Feng*

State Key Laboratory of Bioactive Substance and Function of Natural Medicines, Institute of Materia Medica, Chinese Academy of Medical Sciences and Peking Union Medical College, 2 Nanwei Rd., Xicheng Dist., Beijing 100050, P. R. China

E-mail : fengzhq@imm.ac.cn

Manuscript received online 29 October 2013, accepted 17 February 2014

Abstract : The stereoselective *C*-alkylation of a chiral nitronic acid (4*S**,5*R*)-(+)-4-(6-nitro-6-carbethoxymethyl)-5-[(1*R*)-menthyloxy]-3,4-dihydro-2(5*H*)-furanone which was generally alkylated by alkyl halide giving single *O*-alkylated product, was described. The structure and the absolute configuration of C6 of the two diastereoisomer *C*-alkylated products (7 and 8) were deduced by comprehensive analysis for their spectra data, the dominant conformation and the coupling mechanism of the carbanion of nitro compound 2.

Keywords : Chiral nitronic acid, chiral nitronic ester, *O*-alkylation, *C*-alkylation.

Introduction

The study on nitronic acids and nitronic esters remains relatively rare due to their well instability^{1,2}. Primary and secondary nitro compounds are valuable synthetic intermediates with one widely recognized limitation. The monoanions derived from them are more prone to alkylate on oxygen rather than on carbon in reactions with most alkyl halides³⁻⁵, and the *O*-alkylated products trend to decompose into oximes and carbonyl compounds (Scheme 1).

Alkyl nitroacetates constitute a class of valuable intermediates for the preparation of various organic molecules⁵⁻⁷. Recently, during the study of an asymmetric synthesis of a natural product, we had synthesized a key intermediate, the nitro compound **2** by asymmetric Michael

addition of ethyl nitroacetate to the chiral synthon **1** formed via etherification between (-)-menthol and 5-hydroxy-2(5*H*)-furanone⁵, and found that a stable crystalline of enantiopure nitronic acid **3**, as an enolized isomer of the nitro compound **2**, could be isolated when Michael addition reaction was quenched with ice and water, and spontaneously reverted to **2** when it was left in a solvent for a period of time⁸. In an attempt to obtain a chiral nitro compound (*C*-alkylated product), we treated **3** with 1-bromobutane in the presence of K₂CO₃ and DMF. A white crystalline substance was eventually afforded, which to our surprise was not the expected tertiary nitro compound but was characterized as a butyl nitronic ester of **3** (*O*-alkylated product) by its IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR spectra and elemental analysis. We thus obtained an

Scheme 1. Alkylation of nitro compound.

enantiomerically pure nitronic ester, which was the first example of a nitronic ester produced via *O*-alkylation of the alkali metal salt of a nitro compound with an alkyl halide. Subsequently, we prepared a series of chiral nitronic esters of **3**, but the *C*-alkylated product wasn't found. In recent publications⁸⁻¹⁴, we described the progress in the study of nitronic acids and nitronic esters. However, the *C*-alkylation of the chiral nitronic acid **3** remains unknown. Here we report the *C*-alkylation of the chiral nitronic acid **3**.

Results and discussion

In the study on the *C*-alkylation, we found that treatment of **3** with primary alkyl halides in the presence of K_2CO_3 and DMF at room temperature resulted in the formation of single *O*-alkylated product nitronic ester, and treatment with secondary alkyl halides resulted in the formation of two *O*-alkylated products nitronic ester and *O*-alkyloxime⁸. Then, the active alkyl halides, such as benzyl chloride or benzyl bromide⁸ and ethyl chloroacetate or ethyl bromoacetate were used respectively to react with **3** under the same reaction conditions as mentioned above, likewise the only *O*-alkylated products nitronic esters (**4** for benzyl chloride or benzyl bromide, **5** for ethyl chloroacetate or ethyl bromoacetate) were obtained. However, when *para*-nitrobenzyl chloride and *para*-nitrobenzyl bromide were used respectively to react with **3**, during the course of the reaction and after the workup, we noticed that there were in fact three close spots on our TLC plates. After the workup, three constituents were obtained by careful column chromatography of the crude mixture, a colorless oil was assigned to **6**, two colorless liquids to **7** and **8**, and the ratio of three constituents : **6** : **7** : **8** = 2 : 5 : 1 (Scheme 2).

The molecular structures of the five compounds were identified by means of IR and NMR analysis. The nitronic ester **4**, **5**, **6** and the tertiary nitro compounds (**7** and **8**)

Scheme 2. The alkylation of the chiral nitronic acid **3**.

gave satisfactory elemental analysis, and IR, 1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR data are consistent with their structures (Tables 1–2). The structure of **6** was confirmed by comparing with nitronic esters synthesized before⁸ in the characteristic spectroscopic data such as IR : 1630 cm^{-1} ($C=N$) and ^{13}C NMR : 109 ppm (C6). The IR spectrum of **7** and **8**, as compared to that of **3**, **4**, **5** and **6**, showed a strong absorption at 1580 cm^{-1} ($N=O$, the characteristic absorption of aliphatic nitro compound), with the absence of the absorption at *ca.* 1630 cm^{-1} ($C=N$). The 1H NMR showed a single peak at *ca.* 3.9 ppm ($C-CH_2PhNO_2-p$) different from at *ca.* 5.2 ppm ($O-CH_2PhNO_2-p$), and the signal at *ca.* 3.7 ppm for H4 in **3-6** shifted upfield to *ca.* 3.1 ppm for H4 in **7** or **8**. In the ^{13}C NMR spectra, a striking difference was seen, where the signal at *ca.* 109 for C6 of nitronic acid **3** or nitronic ester **4-6** shifted upfield to *ca.* 95 ppm for C6 in **7** or **8**.

Table 1. The specific rotations and partial IR data (cm^{-1}) of compounds (**3-6**)

Compds.	C=O	C=N	N=O	$[\alpha]_{589}^{25}$
3	1745, 1725, 1680	1635		+52.5° (<i>c</i> 1.4, CH_3Cl)
6	1798, 1740, 1710	1630	1530	+19.5° (<i>c</i> 1.84, acetone)
7	1810, 1760		1580, 1540	-36.8° (<i>c</i> 7.81, acetone)
8	1810, 1770, 1730		1580, 1542	-89.6° (<i>c</i> 0.91, acetone)

Table 2. The partial ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR data (ppm) of compounds (3-6)

Compds.	H3a	H3b	H4	H5	H _{CH₂PhNO_{2-p}}	C6
3	2.6(dd)	2.9(dd)	3.7(dd)	5.4(s)		109.3
6	2.7(dd)	2.9(dd)	3.8(dd)	5.4(s)	5.2(s)	109.8
7	3.3(dd)	3.0(dd)	3.2(m)	5.9(s)	4.0(s)	95.4
8	3.1(dd)	2.7(dd)	3.1(m)	5.9(s)	3.9(s)	94.9

The configuration of the nitronic ester **4-6** obtained herein was confirmed to be *Z* by means of NOE experiment, which are consistent with the configuration of the nitronic esters reported⁸. The enolization of nitro compound **2** could form two configurations, but the *Z* configuration of nitronic acid **3** is more stable, which results from the structure of 6-membered ring linked by hydrogen bond. At the presence of K₂CO₃, the nitronic acid **3** can be converted to the potassium nitronate with the stable structure of 6-membered ring linked by K⁺. Then a nucleophilic substitution occurred when treated with RX, giving the *O*-alkylated product nitronic ester **4-6** as *Z* stereoisomer.

The absolute configuration of C6 in the *C*-alkylated nitro compounds (**7** and **8**) could be deduced by comprehensive analysis for the dominant conformation and the coupling mechanism of the carbanion of nitro compound **2**. At the presence of K₂CO₃, the nitro compound **2** or nitronic acid **3** can be transformed into the carbanion of nitro compound **2**, since the nitro and carbethoxy groups are particularly effective in stabilizing a negative charge on the adjacent carbon. The carbanion along with adjacent carbonyl carbon, nitrogen of nitro and chiral carbon constitute a triangle planar structure, which result from the sp² hybrid of the C6. In the dominant conformation of the carbanion of nitro compound **2** (Fig. 1), the triangle plan is parallel with the angle plan of C6-C4-H4, and the carbethoxy group direct to the side of carbonyl group on lactone ring. The coupling of the carbanion should favor the Si face to give C6(*S*) configuration, as the Re face is highly hindered by bulky menthyl group, the *C*-alkylated nitro compound **7** as a major diastereoisomer, which is identical with the result of **7** : **8** = 5 : 1 (mol ratio). Another diastereoisomer should be *C*-alkylated nitro compound **8** carrying C6(*R*) configuration. The absolute configuration of C6 in the *C*-alkylated nitro compounds should be confirmed by the X-ray diffraction

Fig. 1. The dominant conformation of the carbanion of **2**.

of single crystal, but they are all colourless liquids.

In summary, first stereoselective *C*-alkylation example of the chiral nitronic acid **3** was described, and the structure and the absolute configuration of C6 of the *C*-alkylated nitro compounds (**7** and **8**) were inferred on base of the comprehensive analysis for their spectra data, the dominant conformation and the coupling mechanism of the carbanion of nitro compound **2**.

Experimental

Unless otherwise indicated, all reagents and solvents were the best commercial grades available and were not purified further. ¹H NMR and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on a DMX 300-MHz spectrometer using CDCl₃ as the solvent and TMS as the internal standard with

Scheme 3. The inference of the configurations of alkylated products.

coupling constant (J) in Hertz. IR spectra were performed on a Hitachi 260-50 spectrometer. UV spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-240 spectrometer.

Nitronic acid **3** were prepared by Kang's methods⁸.

O-Alkylation and C-alkylation of chiral nitronic acid (3) :

Nitronic acid **3** (3 g, 8 mmol) and finely ground anhydrous K_2CO_3 (1.2 g, 8.7 mmol) were mixed in DMF (20 mL). Nitrogen gas was bubbled through the suspension, and placed under a positive pressure of nitrogen. After 10 min, to this well-stirred suspension was added dropwise a solution of *p*-nitrobenzyl bromide (1.73 g, 8 mmol) in DMF (10 ml). The mixture was stirred at room temperature, and the progress of the reaction was monitored by TLC. When the alkylating agent had disappeared, 30 ml ether was added and filtered. The filtrate was washed with saturated aqueous $NaHCO_3$ solution, water and saturated sodium chloride, and then dried over anhydrous sodium sulfate. The solvent was removed on a rotary evaporator under reduced pressure to give crude products, which was carefully isolated by column chromatography on silica gel using a mixture of light petroleum and ethyl acetate (5 : 1) as the eluent, giving *O*-alkylated product **6** and *C*-alkylated products **7** and **8**.

(Z)-(+)-Carbethoxy methene nitronic ester of (4S,5R)-4-(6-nitro-6-carbethoxymethyl)-5-[(1R)-menthyloxy]-3,4-dihydro-2(5H)-furanone (5)* :

A colorless oil, yield : 72%; $[\alpha]_{589}^{25} + 47.7^\circ$ (c 12.83, acetone); IR (neat) : 1750, 1700, 1638 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR : δ 0.66–1.11 (14H, m), 1.19–1.29 (6H, m), 1.54–1.58 (2H, m), 2.06–2.11 (2H, m), 2.66 (1H, dd, J 11.1, 7.5 Hz), 2.88 (1H, dd, J 11.1, 3.3 Hz), 3.40 (1H, m), 3.76 (1H, dd, J 7.5, 3.3 Hz), 4.16 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 4.24 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 4.53 (1H, d, J 15.6 Hz), 4.62 (1H, d, J 15.6 Hz), 5.38 (1H, s); ^{13}C NMR : 14.9, 15.0, 16.8, 21.8, 22.9, 23.8, 26.1, 32.4, 33.6, 34.9, 43.8, 47.8, 48.9, 61.9, 62.4, 62.7, 82.7, 104.0, 110.4, 159.3, 168.1, 170.4; Anal. Calcd. for $C_{22}H_{35}O_9N$: C, 57.76; H, 7.66; N, 3.06 wt.%. Found : C, 57.65; H, 7.38; N, 2.98 wt.%.

(Z)-(+)-p-Nitrobenzyl nitronic ester of (4S,5R)-4-(6-nitro-6-carbethoxymethyl)-5-[(1R)-menthyloxy]-3,4-dihydro-2(5H)-furanone (6)* :

A colorless oil, yield : 20%; $[\alpha]_{589}^{25} + 19.5^\circ$ (c 1.84, acetone); IR (neat) : 1798, 1740, 1710, 1630, 1530

cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR : δ 0.73–0.95 (11H, m), 1.22–1.44 (3H, t), 1.33 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 1.63 (2H, m), 2.15 (2H, m), 2.71 (1H, dd, J 10.8, 7.5 Hz), 2.90 (1H, dd, J 10.8, 3.6 Hz), 3.38 (1H, m), 3.78 (1H, dd, J 7.5, 3.6 Hz), 4.30 (2H, q, J 7.2 Hz), 5.24 (2H, s), 5.38 (1H, s), 7.51 (2H, d, J 8.7 Hz), 8.19 (2H, d, J 8.7 Hz); Anal. Calcd. for $C_{25}H_{34}O_9N_2$: C, 59.29; H, 6.72; N, 2.76 wt.%. Found : C, 59.41; H, 6.58; N, 2.59 wt.%.

(6S,4S*,5R)-(-)-4-(6-Nitro-6-carbethoxy-6-p-nitrobenzyl tertiary alkyl)-5-[(1R)-menthyloxy]-3,4-dihydro-2(5H)-furanone (7)* :

A colorless oil, yield : 50%; $[\alpha]_{589}^{25} - 36.8^\circ$ (c 7.81, acetone); UV λ_{max} : 262.9 nm (EtOH); IR (neat) : 1810, 1760, 1580, 1540 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR : δ 0.75–1.25 (11H, m), 1.37 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 1.30–1.45 (2H, m), 1.60–1.75 (2H, m), 2.10–2.18 (2H, m), 2.20–2.28 (1H, m), 2.92–3.05 (1H, dd, J 18.0, 2.6 Hz), 3.25–3.38 (1H, dd, J 18.0, 9.6 Hz), 3.14–3.18 (1H, m), 3.59–3.62 (1H, m), 4.01 (2H, s), 4.30–4.50 (2H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 5.86 (1H, s), 7.61 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 8.30 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz); ^{13}C NMR : 13.6, 15.4, 20.8, 22.1, 22.9, 25.4, 30.1, 31.3, 34.1, 39.3, 39.6, 44.7, 47.6, 77.7, 64.4, 95.4, 100.2, 124.1, 131.0 \times 2, 138.9 \times 2, 147.9, 164.3, 173.1; MS (FAB m/z) : 507 (M+1); Anal. Calcd. for $C_{25}H_{34}O_9N_2$: C, 59.29; H, 6.72; N, 5.53 wt.%. Found : C, 59.56; H, 6.35; N, 5.41 wt.%.

(6R,4S*,5R)-(-)-4-(6-nitro-6-carbethoxy-6-p-nitrobenzyl tertiary alkyl)-5-[(1R)-menthyloxy]-3,4-dihydro-2(5H)-furanone (8)* :

A colorless oil, yield : 10%; $[\alpha]_{589}^{25} - 89.56^\circ$ (c 0.91, acetone); UV λ_{max} : 262.6 nm (EtOH); IR (neat) : 1810, 1765, 1725, 1580, 1545 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR : δ 0.7–1.2 (11H, m), 1.30 (3H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 1.25–1.35 (1H, m), 1.35–1.50 (1H, m), 1.6–1.72 (2H, m), 2.00–2.15 (2H, m), 2.30–2.40 (1H, m), 2.70–2.80 (1H, dd, J 17.7, 3.3 Hz), 3.12–3.20 (1H, dd, J 17.7, 9.6 Hz), 3.06–3.10 (1H, m), 3.50–3.60 (1H, m), 3.88 (2H, s), 4.30–4.40 (2H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 5.88 (1H, s), 7.55 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 8.22 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz); ^{13}C NMR : 12.0, 14.0, 19.4, 20.6, 21.8, 24.0, 28.7, 30.1, 33.0, 38.4 \times 2, 44.2, 46.6, 75.9, 62.9, 94.9, 98.5, 122.5 \times 2, 130.7 \times 2, 139.3, 146.8, 163.5, 172.1; MS (FAB m/z) : 507 (M+1); Anal. Calcd. for $C_{25}H_{34}O_9N_2$: C, 59.29; H, 6.72; N, 5.53 wt.%. Found : C, 59.35; H, 6.56; N, 5.21 wt.%.

Zhang *et al.* : The stereoselective C-alkylation of chiral nitronic acid (4*S**,5*R*)-(+)-4-(6-nitro- *etc.*

References

1. K. B. G. Torrsell, "Nitrile Oxides, Nitrones and Nitronates in Organic Synthesis", VCH, New York, 1988.
2. E. Breuer, "The Chemistry of Amino, Nitroso and Nitro Compounds and their Derivatives", 1982.
3. P. A. Wade, S. D. Wade and S. A. Hardinger, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1982, **47**, 365.
4. D. Seebach, E. W. Colvin, F. Lehr and T. Weller, *Chimia*, 1979, **33**, 1.
5. M. T. Shipchandler, *Synthesis*, 1979, 666.
6. E. Keller and B. L. Feringa, *Synlett*, 1997, 842.
7. M. Sawamura, Y. Nakayama, W. M. Tang and Y. Ito, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1996, **61**, 9090.
8. F. A. Kang and C. L. Yin, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1996, **61**, 5523.
9. F. A. Kang and C. L. Yin, *Tetrahedron*, 1998, **54**, 13155.
10. F. A. Kang and C. L. Yin, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **119**, 8562.
11. F. A. Kang, C. L. Yin and S. W. She, *Chin. Sci. Bull.*, 1996, **41**, 1847.
12. F. A. Kang, H. Y. Yin and C. L. Yin, *Chin. Sci. Bull.*, 1997, **42**, 1628.
13. F. A. Kang and C. L. Yin, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1997, 579.
14. F. A. Kang and C. L. Yin, *Tetrahedron : Asymmetry*, 1997, **8**, 3585.

